

Supplementary Materials

van Kessel et al. A scoping review and expert consensus on digital determinants of health.

Table of Contents

eTable 1. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist	3
eTable 2. Search strings for each database or search engine.	5
eResults 1. Non-English records that were excluded based on language restrictions.	6
eTable 3. Total results of the consensus process.....	7

eTable 1. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	4
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	5-6
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	6
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	6
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	7
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	7
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	7-8, eTable 2
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	8
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	NA
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	NA
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	NA
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	8, eMethods 1
RESULTS			

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	9
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	eTable 3
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	NA
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	NA
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	10-13
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	13-17, 19-20
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	18-19
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	20
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	24

eTable 2. Search strings for each database or search engine.

Database/Search engine	Query	# hits
Medline, Embase (Ovid)	<p>1 (online or digital or virtual or Internet or AI or "artificial intelligence" or telehealth or telemedicine or ehealth or e-health).ti,ab.</p> <p>2 Telemedicine/</p> <p>3 1 or 2</p> <p>4 ("social determinant*" or "structural determinant*" or "socioeconomic factor*" or education or income or poverty or employment or housing or gender or ethnicity or race).ti,ab.</p> <p>5 Employment/ or Housing/ or Poverty/ or Income/ or Education/ or Schools/ or Literacy/ or Socioeconomic Factors/</p> <p>6 ("commercial determinant*" or ((commercial or corporate) and determinant* and (health or disease*)) or CDoH).ti,ab.</p> <p>7 "political determinant*".ti,ab.</p> <p>8 (democracy or autocracy or "welfare regime" or "welfare state" or "welfare capitalism" or politics or "political tradition" or internationality or globalization).ti,ab.</p> <p>9 (health or "health service*").ti,ab.</p> <p>10 8 and 9</p> <p>11 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 10</p> <p>12 3 and 11</p> <p>13 ("systematic review" or "scoping review" or "realist review" or "integrative review" or "umbrella review").ti,ab.</p> <p>14 12 and 13</p> <p>15 limit 14 to yr="2018 -Current"</p> <p>16 limit 15 to "remove preprint records"</p>	5479
Web of Science	<p>TS=(online or digital or virtual or Internet or AI or "artificial intelligence" or telehealth or telemedicine or ehealth or e-health) AND (TS=("social determinant*" or "structural determinant*" or "socioeconomic factor*" or education or income or poverty or employment or housing or gender or ethnicity or race) OR TS=("commercial determinant*" or "corporate determinant*" or "political determinant*")) AND TS=("systematic review" or "scoping review" or "realist review" or "integrative review" or "umbrella review")</p>	5309
PubMed (non-systematic)	<p>(digital[Title/Abstract] OR online[Title/Abstract] OR virtual[Title/Abstract] OR internet[Title/Abstract] OR telehealth[Title/Abstract] OR ehealth[Title/Abstract] OR AI[Title/Abstract] OR "Artificial Intelligence"[Title/Abstract]) AND ("social determinants of health"[Title/Abstract] OR SDoH[Title/Abstract] OR "commercial determinants of health"[Title/Abstract] OR CDoH[Title/Abstract] OR "political determinants of health"[Title/Abstract] OR PDoH[Title/Abstract])</p>	823
Google Scholar (non-systematic)	<p>"AI" "social determinants of health"</p> <p>"digital" "social determinants of health"</p> <p>"AI" "commercial determinants of health"</p> <p>"digital" "commercial determinants of health"</p> <p>"AI" "political determinants of health"</p> <p>"digital" "political determinants of health"</p> <p>"digital determinants of health"</p>	<p>300</p> <p>300</p> <p>300</p> <p>300</p> <p>300</p> <p>300</p> <p>300</p>

eResults 1. Non-English records that were excluded based on language restrictions.

Chahdi, M., Bruchhäuser, A., von Gahlen-Hoops, W. et al. (2023). Interventionen zur Reduzierung der Krankenhauswiederaufnahmeraten bei Patient:innen mit COPD: eine systematische Literaturrecherche. *Med Klin Intensivmed Notfmed*, 118: 584–591. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00063-023-01003-0>

Vila, M., Oliveira, V.R., Agustí, A. (2023). Telemedicina en el manejo de la enfermedad pulmonar obstructiva crónica: revisión sistemática. *Medicina Clínica*, 160(8): 355-363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.medcli.2023.01.008>

徐文浩,田熙,艾合太木江·安外尔,瞿元元,施国海,张海梁 & 叶定伟. (2022). 人工智能在泌尿系统肿瘤中的应用研究进展. *中国癌症杂志*, 1: 68-74. <https://10.19401/j.cnki.1007-3639.2022.01.009>.

Reumann, M.K., Braun, B.J., Menger, M.M. et al. (2022). Künstliche Intelligenz und Ausblick auf Anwendungsfelder in der Pseudarthrosentherapie. *Unfallchirurgie*, 125: 611–618. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00113-022-01202-y>

Tazawa, Y. (2014). コンパニオン診断薬の開発と運用に向けた現状課題と展望. *Yakugaku zasshi: Journal of the Pharmaceutical Society of Japan*, 134(4): 491-498. <https://doi.org/10.1248/yakushi.13-00248-5>

Wang, Y. (2023). 临床脊柱外科治疗的新兴技术发展前沿与展望. *Zhonghua wai ke za zhi*, 62(1): 16-21. <https://doi.org/10.3760/cma.j.cn112139-20230926-00142>

Müller, L., Kloeckner, R., Mildenerger, P. et al. (2023). Validierung und Implementierung von künstlicher Intelligenz in der radiologischen Versorgung. *Radiologie*, 63: 381–386. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00117-022-01097-1>

eTable 3. Total results of the consensus process.

Layer	Determinant	Round 1 (n = 35)			Round 2 (n = 32)		
		Median (IQR)	Urgency percentage	Urgency category	Median (IQR)	Urgency percentage	Urgency category
Digital domain							
Person-specific determinants	Device and software availability	4 (2)	64.86	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	81.82	High urgency
	Internet access and connectivity	5 (1)	86.11	High urgency
	Problematic device and internet use	4 (1)	64.86	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	75.76	Moderate urgency
	Digital self-efficacy, empowerment, and altruism	3 (2)	44.44	Low urgency
	Digital literacy	4 (1)	80.56	High urgency
	Use of virtual private networks	2 (1)	13.89	Low urgency
	Cyberbullying	4 (1)	61.11	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	57.58	Moderate urgency
	Attitude towards digital solutions	4 (1)	59.46	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	75.76	Moderate urgency
Community determinants	Provision of digital training courses	4 (1)	57.14	Moderate urgency			
	Data and digital capacity	4 (1)	80	High urgency			
	Digital penetration & implementation incentives	4 (1)	54.29	Moderate urgency			
	Infosphere	3 (1)	45.71	Low urgency			
	Implicit tech bias	4 (1)	51.43	Moderate urgency			
Technology-related determinants	Gamification	2 (1)	20	Low urgency
	Moderation of harmful content & misinformation	4 (1)	88.57	High urgency
	Explainability	4 (1)	76.47	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	93.75	High urgency
	Ambient intelligence	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
	Model accuracy & algorithmic validation	5 (1)	80	High urgency
	Personal customizability	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Data and digital interoperability	5 (1)	91.43	High urgency
	Reliance on internet	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Security settings and features	4 (2)	71.43	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	90.62	High urgency
	Firewall protection	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
Policy determinants	AI validation, transparency, explainability, accountability, & ethics	5 (1)	91.43	High urgency
	Data consent policy	4 (2)	74.29	Moderate urgency	5 (1)	87.5	High urgency
	Privacy and security policy	4 (1)	80	High urgency
	Access and sharing policy	4 (1)	82.86	High urgency
	Mis/disinformation policy	4 (1)	80	High urgency
	Outcomes, utility, & value sharing	4 (2)	57.14	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	84.38	High urgency
Political, economic, societal, and	Public-private-person partnerships	4 (1)	51.43	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	53.12	Moderate urgency
	Digital divides	4 (1)	94.29	High urgency

cultural determinants	Financial investments and conditions	4 (1)	57.14	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	68.75	Moderate urgency
	Data governance & ethics	5 (1)	85.71	High urgency
	Data culture	4 (1)	62.86	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	81.25	High urgency
	Digital public infrastructure	4 (1)	91.43	High urgency
	Right to scientific advancement	3 (2)	31.43	Low urgency
	Regulatory mandate	4 (1)	62.86	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	90.62	High urgency
Social domain							
Person-specific determinants	Health literacy	4 (2)	69.44	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	78.79	Moderate urgency
	Education level	4 (2)	64.86	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	78.79	Moderate urgency
	Race/ethnicity	4 (1)	52.78	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	57.58	Moderate urgency
	Housing	3 (2)	44.44	Low urgency
	Migration status	3 (2)	36.11	Low urgency
	Legal identity	3 (2)	40.54	Low urgency
	Health/disability status	4 (1)	75.68	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	93.94	High urgency
	Employment status	3.5 (1)	50	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	66.67	Moderate urgency
	Sex	3 (2)	27.78	Low urgency
	Science literacy	3 (2)	27.78	Low urgency
	Age	3.5 (2)	50	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	63.64	Moderate urgency
	Urbanicity	2 (1)	22.22	Low urgency
	Physical activity	3 (2)	40.54	Low urgency
	Access to health and social services	5 (1)	81.08	High urgency
	Food security	3 (2)	44.44	Low urgency
	Impulsivity	2 (1)	13.89	Low urgency
	Social skills	2.5 (1)	16.67	Low urgency
Emotional regulation	2.5 (1)	25	Low urgency	
Gender identity	3 (1)	24.32	Low urgency	
Community determinants	Social support	4 (2)	57.14	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	62.5	Moderate urgency
	Organizational culture	3 (1)	40	Low urgency
	Institutional workflow	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Propensity to change	3 (2)	34.29	Low urgency
	Community participation & engagement	4 (2)	62.86	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	71.88	Moderate urgency
Technology-related determinants	Inclusive design	4 (2)	68.57	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	81.25	High urgency
	Good practice design	4 (2)	65.71	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	87.50	High urgency
Policy determinants	Employment & labour policy	3 (1)	34.29	Low urgency
	Health and social care policy	5 (1)	85.71	High urgency
	Education policy	4 (2)	60	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	71.88	Moderate urgency
	Urban-rural planning and development	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
Political, economic, societal, and	Cultural and social norms and values	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Religion	2 (2)	5.71	Low urgency

cultural determinants	Socioeconomic inequalities	4 (2)	74.29	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	90.62	High urgency
Commercial and economic domain							
Person-specific determinants	Financial literacy	3 (1)	25	Low urgency
	Consumer literacy	3 (2)	36.11	Low urgency
	Financial stability	3 (2)	37.84	Low urgency
	Access to financial services	3 (2)	37.84	Low urgency
	Online spending habits	2 (1)	21.62	Low urgency
Community determinants	Supply chain	3 (2)	37.14	Low urgency
	Corporate governance	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Enterprise architecture	3 (2)	28.57	Low urgency
	Market coverage of digital strategies	3 (2)	28.57	Low urgency
	ICT reliance	3 (2)	42.86	Low urgency
	Labour practices	3 (1)	42.86	Low urgency
	Waste management	3 (1)	20	Low urgency
	Change management	4 (2)	60	Moderate urgency	5 (2)	71.88	Moderate urgency
	Scientific practices	4 (1)	57.14	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	62.5	Moderate urgency
	Reputational management	2 (1)	14.29	Low urgency
Technology-related determinants	Product design philosophy	3 (1)	40	Low urgency
	Corporate social responsibility	3 (1)	37.14	Low urgency
	Online health-harming goods and service retail	4 (1)	54.29	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	62.50	Moderate urgency
	Dark commercial patterns	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
	Targeted marketing and nudging	4 (1)	54.29	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	62.50	Moderate urgency
Policy determinants	Service provision	4 (2)	57.14	Moderate urgency	4 (2)	59.38	Moderate urgency
	Economic and financial policies	4 (2)	54.29	Moderate urgency	4 (2)	68.75	Moderate urgency
	Intellectual property & patent policy	3 (2)	48.57	Low urgency			
	Regulation of market and marketing strategies for digital contexts	4 (2)	60	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	75	Moderate urgency
Political, economic, societal, and cultural determinants	News & media	4 (1)	54.29	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	59.38	Moderate urgency
	Environment	3 (2)	48.57	Low urgency
	Commercial influence	3 (1)	45.71	Low urgency
	Degree of privatization	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Financialization	3 (2)	34.29	Low urgency
	Lobbying	3 (2)	34.29	Low urgency
	Economic stability	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Internationalisation of trade & investment	3 (1)	20	Low urgency
Political economy of globalization	3 (2)	40	Low urgency	
Political domain							
Person-specific determinants	Civic literacy	3 (2)	38.89	Low urgency
	Epistemic competence	3 (2)	36.11	Low urgency
Community determinants	Political messaging	3 (2)	31.43	Low urgency
	Ownership of technology	4 (1)	65.71	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	81.25	High urgency

	Political engagement & agenda setting	4 (2)	51.43	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	62.5	Moderate urgency
	Regional networks	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
	Enfranchisement of marginalised groups	4 (1)	62.86	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	78.12	Moderate urgency
	Power asymmetries	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency
Technology-related determinants	Political biases	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Extension of public space	3 (2)	31.43	Low urgency
Policy determinants	Governance of commercial markets	3 (1)	42.86	Low urgency
	Defense, security & justice	3 (2)	42.86	Low urgency
	Political influence on campaigns	3 (2)	31.43	Low urgency
	Commodification and product-focus of science & technology	3 (2)	31.43	Low urgency			
Political, economic, societal, and cultural determinants	Digitalisation agenda	4 (1)	65.71	Moderate urgency	4 (0)	84.38	High urgency
	Geopolitical landscape, competition & collaboration	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Scientific autonomy & independence	4 (1)	51.43	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	56.25	Moderate urgency
	Accountability and transparency of commercial interests	4 (2)	68.57	Moderate urgency	5 (1)	84.38	High urgency
	Local political environment	3 (2)	40	Low urgency
	Open and transparent decision-making	4 (1)	77.14	Moderate urgency	4 (1)	93.75	High urgency
	Political origins of existing inequalities	3 (1)	42.86	Low urgency
	Corporate capture	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Development of digital government	3 (1)	48.57	Low urgency
	Sensitivity to false equivalence	3 (2)	45.71	Low urgency